

PROSPECTS OF ATTRACTING CAPITAL THROUGH THE STOCK MARKET IN UZBEKISTAN

Ismailov Musabek

researcher

Tashkent State University of Economics,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8433570>

Economic reforms implemented in our country in recent years are becoming a tradition of drawing up road maps and developing development concepts involving internationally experienced specialists and experts. In particular, the concept of the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2035, which is considered the main road map for attracting investments, according to the information provided by the international non-governmental and non-profit organization "Buyuk Nekavit" includes "the share of the capital market of 0.1% of the total investment financing source in Uzbekistan in 2019" it will increase by 3, 7, 19% in 2025, 2030, 2035, respectively. Of course, future plans based on these calculations and ensuring this development will be possible only by solving many problematic relationships.

Decree No. PF-6096 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 27, 2020 "On measures to accelerate the reform of state-owned enterprises and privatization of state assets" was adopted as one of the important steps in achieving the above-mentioned results and liberalizing the economy. According to this decree, the list of 479 "Enterprises whose state share packages (shares) are sold to the private sector in full through public auctions" was approved in Uzbekistan, however, it would be appropriate to implement some systematic approaches to the realization of such a large amount of state shares. Because there is a high probability that investors will not have enough funds to meet such a large offer. Therefore, it is necessary to increase the role of investment funds (IF) in order to gather financial resources for these funds to accumulate capital and satisfy offers, and to create opportunities for investors with relatively little financial resources to participate in these transactions. For this purpose, IFs can attract financial resources and invest by presenting to the public all information about privatized enterprises that are attractive for investment (profits of recent years, dividends paid to shareholders or shareholders, forecasts of the level of profitability for investors in the future, etc.) in the form of a brief information source. will be able to increase their capabilities.

Some of the enterprises that were determined to be sold on the basis of the above decree were previously sold in accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 9, 2019 No. Until April 1, 2020, the "sale of shares in the charter capital" was set. However, some of them were not sold due to lack of demand from investors. In particular, the 73.87% state share of JSC "Testing oil and gas wells", which we studied in our research work, was put up for auction on May 29, 2020 at RFB "Tashkent" in connection with the implementation of the decision, and there was no opportunity to privatize the state shares for almost five months.

Taking this into account, the introduction of the following mechanisms of the "Book-building" method, which we considered in the first chapter of our research work, will give positive results in improving the process of implementing public offers in our country:

1. Using the weighted average value method in determining prices in IPOs. That is, in this case, the price that received the most votes in the applications submitted by investors is determined as the crossing price, and trades are carried out at this price. In this way, the price with the highest number of votes determines the highest level of demand among the general investors and expresses the fair implementation of the price determination in IPOs;

2. Optimizing the distribution of securities to investors during IPOs by setting limits on the composition of investors using the Indian experience presented in the first chapter in the process of IPOs (taking into account the interests of both institutional and retail investors), and after the IPO, the issuer's corporate governance process has a positive effect (the "monopoly" in making management decisions is eliminated as a result of the diversification of the composition of shareholders). In particular, taking into account the world experience in conducting IPOs in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to introduce the practice of distributing at least 25 percent of the offered shares to retail investors.

In the conditions of the market economy, each corporate structure implements the financial resources necessary for the implementation or development of its activities in the form that is most optimal for itself. First of all, it is necessary to take as a benchmark the strategic goal aimed at increasing the assets of the shareholders of the corporate structure (shareholders, etc.). However, in enterprises with a state share (especially with a high state share), the first-order characteristics of this goal often recede. In particular, according to the data of the central depository in our country, a total of 595 joint-stock

companies have 148.7 trillion. Soum shares were issued, of which the state share is 126.9 trillion in 257 JSCs. Soums or 85.4% of the total amount" (as of 01.09.2020), it should be said that reducing the state share in JSCs of our country is important not only for the development of the private sector, but also for the improvement of corporate governance in privatized JSCs and their economic development.

Attracting investments for the purpose of economic development is an important task for all countries. Organization of expanded reproduction, implementation of strategic development programs, acquisition of new markets require additional capital investments. Therefore, the choice of the most appropriate sources of financing investment projects in corporate structures has a direct impact on the profitability and profitability of this investment project in the future. In this case, it is important for corporate structures to decide which method, form and mechanism to use for attracting the financial resources they need based on careful calculations, and to attract the most appropriate (cheapest, fastest and does not negatively affect the capital structure) capital for them. Therefore, ensuring the mandatory consideration of alternative options when attracting financial resources in our country, especially in corporate structures with a state share, is of great importance in the development of our economy in the future (taking into account the high level of the share of enterprises with a state share).

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